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A SCIENTIFIC METHOD FOR INTERNATIONAL TAXATION?*

Luiza Leite de Queiroz**

ABSTRACT

Fractioning and fairly distributing parts of a whole is never quite straightforward. Whether we speak of justly portioning and dividing scrambled eggs between siblings or jurisdictional claims over the ocean space between nations, reckoning with the dilemmas of sharing is an integral part of the human experience. Acknowledging that, this essay contends that contemporary discussions on fairness in international taxation ought to be situated within this broader context. It is centrally argued that justly allocating taxing entitlements over cross-border wealth is a task contingent on the same subjective predicaments seen in the division process of any given valuable whole. The analysis proceeds by reference to two proposed elements, namely unrestrained perception of value and nature of the divided thing. In conclusion, it is reasoned that, while a strictly objective (often termed scientific) conception of international taxation is unattainable, a less biased version, inspired by double-blind methodology, may be within reach.

I. HAVE YOUR CAKE AND EAT IT TOO

Growing up in a large family teaches one many valuable lessons in life. Navigating the fine complexities of harmonious coexistence requires soft skills and a great deal of mutual understanding. Above all, one lesson remains acutely relevant beyond the confines of familial bonds: sharing may be caring but it can also be tricky. Fractioning and fairly¹ distributing parts of a whole is never quite straightforward, whether it be scrambled eggs between siblings or birthday cake between a plethora of cousins. Whichever the case may be, rules must be devised to soothe and appease a battalion of competing interests. A staple within many families' squabble dissipation toolbox is the famed *divide-and-choose* rule

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¹ The notions of 'fair(ness)' and 'just(ice)' are used interchangeably throughout this essay.

whereby one child portions a whole of something and the other gets to choose their preferred fraction. Extrapolating from this social microcosmos, it is relatively easy to draw parallels between such prosaic *quid pro quos* and broader issues around justly segmenting and assigning parts of a finite whole.

Underlying divide-and-choose is the less-than-revolutionary premise that the partitioner should never be the chooser and vice-versa. Echoing perhaps our most innate senses of what is fair in matters of distribution such token of popular wisdom has, unsurprisingly, long been at the epicentre of academic inquiries. John Rawls' account of pure procedural justice, an integral part of his highly influential views on distributive justice, is indeed illustrated by a modality of the rule.² While not synonymous with the philosopher's much broader theory of justice, the analogy has incidentally been scrutinised over the years via comprehensive responses to Rawls' claims.³ Attempts to defend,⁴ relativise,⁵ and disprove⁶ the rule's latent conceptions of justice and its *true fair* character distinctly flourish in the literature.

Among the many division processes that can be examined through a divide-and-choose lens, this essay is concerned with one in particular: taxing rights over cross-border generated wealth. Processes surrounding the allocation of taxing entitlements between countries have been historically cumbersome.⁷ Some of the decisions that resulted from these processes stick out like a sore thumb to this day⁸ due, in no small measure, to the fact that the partitioners of a whole also got to be the choosers of their preferred fractions.⁹ But at this pivotal

² JOHN RAWLS, *A THEORY OF JUSTICE* 74 (Harvard University Press 2nd revised ed. 1999).

³ Robert Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* 183 (Blackwell. 1974) (remarking that, following publication of *A Theory of Justice*, political philosophers must either work within Rawls' theory or explain why they are not doing so).

⁴ See Samuel Freeman, *Rawls on Distributive Justice and Difference Principle*, in *THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE* (Serena Olsaretti ed. 2018); THOMAS W. POGGE, *REALIZING RAWLS* 185 (Cornell University Press. 1989).

⁵ See David Miller, *Distributive Justice: What the People Think*, 102 *ETHICS* 555 (1992); William Thomson & Hal R. Varian, *Theories of Justice Based on Symmetry*. 7 March 1984.

⁶ See Randall G. Holcombe, *Absence of Envy Does Not Imply Fairness*, 63 *SOUTHERN ECONOMIC JOURNAL* 797 (1997).

⁷ NIKKI J. TEO, *THE UNITED NATIONS IN GLOBAL TAX COORDINATION HIDDEN HISTORY AND POLITICS* (Cambridge University Press. 2023); SUNITA JOGARAJAN, *DOUBLE TAXATION AND THE LEAGUE OF NATIONS* (2018).

⁸ Sunita Jogarajan, *The 100th Anniversary of International Institutions and International Taxation*, 48 *INTERTAX* 929 (2020).

⁹ Which would roughly correspond to the power to tax different categories of active and passive (corporate) income and the consequent division of countries in either *source* or *residence* countries. The existence of embedded biases in favour of residence countries (which are typically capital exporting developed nations) was acknowledged at the very start of the international tax regime in the 1923 Report on Double Taxation drafted by the so-called Four Economists. See Bruins, et al., *Report on Double Taxation Submitted to the*

moment in time in the trajectory of international taxation¹⁰ yet another analysis that aims to highlight the why's and how's of the international tax regime's disequilibrium¹¹ would frankly be trite. What we need at this point instead is unorthodox thinking in how we may gradually reintroduce balance in the regime as we continue to move forwards.

The remainder of this essay will proceed as follows. First, it will briefly state the issue addressed, namely a discourse of scientism in international taxation which seeks to both give distributional matters a varnish of neutrality, as well as to isolate the field from other remits of knowledge that explicitly engage with considerations of fairness. Secondly, it will set a scheme, grounded on one subjective and one objective element, against which international taxation will be situated and compared as yet another distributional problem. Thirdly, it will examine the goal of objectivity in science, its limitations, and the implications of a standard of scientific integrity to a scientific method of international taxation. Finally, in recognition of the perhaps aspirational character of some of the propositions advanced, a pragmatic corrective mechanism for international taxation, inspired by double-blind methodology, will be proposed before some conclusions are drawn.

II. EMPIRICISM, SCIENTISM, AND FAIR DIVISION

Modern international taxation has, for better or worse, long indulged a discourse of near-heedless empiricism.¹² Championed by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD),¹³ the belief that economic

Financial Committee. Geneva, 5 April (1923) (“On the other hand, the debtor countries would no doubt be very reluctant to accept method 2, for the reasons that it would be the most burdensome to their exchequer, and, second, that it does violence to what are at present their instinctive ideas as to their rights to origin taxation”).

¹⁰ Particularly as the United Nations rapidly moves to shift the centre of gravity of norm production in international taxation, as evidenced by the recent adoption of a resolution by the General Assembly which calls for the drafting of a United Nations framework convention on international tax cooperation. See UN General Assembly, *Report of the Secretary-General: Promotion of inclusive and effective international tax cooperation at the United Nations* (15 Nov. 2023).

¹¹ See, e.g. Kim Brooks & Richard Krever, *The Troubling Role of Tax Treaties*, in TAX DESIGN ISSUES WORLDWIDE (Geerten M M Michiels & Victor Thuronyi eds., 2015); Tsilly Dagan, *The Tax Treaties Myth*, 32 NEW YORK UNIVERSITY JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW AND POLITICS (2000); Charles R. Irish, *International double taxation agreements and income taxation at source*, 23 INTERNATIONAL AND COMPARATIVE LAW QUARTERLY 292 (1974).

¹² Allison Christians, *Taxing According to Value Creation*, 90 TAX NOTES INTERNATIONAL 1379, 5 (2018).

¹³ *The OECD as an Actor in International Politics*, in Mechanisms of OECD Governance: International Incentives for National Policy-Making? 14, (Kerstin Martens & Anja P. Jakobi eds., 2010) (noting that policy recommendations are usually not overtly influenced by political considerations and so need to rest on arguments that carry some degree of scientific authority even if this has clear limits).

empiricism, and a specific one¹⁴ at that, is the hallmark of *scientifically endorsed* policy is all-pervading in current international tax debates.¹⁵ Further sustained by a model of mixed legal-scientific governance¹⁶ that seeks to integrate law with social science, the belief has acquired quasi-axiom status in expert circles. In practice, this means that the more fundamental issue of determining which queries empirical methods are capable of fully answering has all but been adjourned.¹⁷

By no means an attack on empiricism,¹⁸ this observation solely wishes to signal the perils of unreflectively portraying empirical scientific methods as the answer to all woes.¹⁹ While it is clear that empirics have much to contribute to responsible public decision-making, it is equally unambiguous that, try as it may, it cannot fully resolve distributional conflicts that ultimately arise from the interaction of competing views on fairness.²⁰ The considerations adduced in this essay modestly attempt to sketch out general lines of reasoning to demonstrate

¹⁴ Eugene Rotwein, *Empiricism and Economic Method: Several Views Considered*, 7 *Journal of Economic Issues* 361 (1973) (emphasising that diversity within economic scholarship has meant that competing positions on empiricism in economic methodology have emerged).

¹⁵ Well-illustrated by the latest developments regarding both Amounts under Pillar One of the so-called Two Pillar Solution. See OECD, *Public Consultation Document Pillar One - Amount B*. (2023); OECD, *Progress Report on the Administration and Tax Certainty Aspects of Amount A of Pillar One*. (2022).

¹⁶ Andrew Lang, *New Legal Realism, Empiricism, and Scientism: The Relative Objectivity of Law and Social Science*, 28 *LEIDEN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW* 231, 233 (2015).

¹⁷ Morris R. Cohen, *Reason and nature: an essay on the meaning of scientific method* 161 (Routledge, 2020) (“The identification of empiricism with the scientific attitude is just a bit of natural complacency. The excessive worship of facts too often hides a disinclination to enter into a genuine inquiry as to whether they are so”).

¹⁸ Casting aside broader philosophical musings on the problem of demarcation of science, particularly Karl Popper’s propositions on falsifiability, the significance of empirical methods to the advancement of scientific knowledge over the centuries hardly requires extensive acclamations here. For Popper’s theory of falsifiability see: KARL POPPER, *THE LOGIC OF SCIENTIFIC DISCOVERY* (Routledge, 2002).

¹⁹ Frank H. Knight, *Institutionalism and Empiricism in Economics* 42 *THE AMERICAN ECONOMIC REVIEW* 45 (19) (illustrating the limits to economic rationale and empiricism in economics).

²⁰ Cecilia Albin, *Negotiating Justice: From Conflict to Agreement*, *International Negotiation* 1 (2022) (analysing how different conceptions of justice influence the outcome of international negotiations).

that international taxation, albeit peculiar in its own way,²¹ should not be given a free epistemological pass of basking in perpetual exception glory.²²

International taxation debates are, congenitally, distributional debates²³ and, as such, share one cardinal commonality with every other distributional debate ever had. That is, that no amount of strictly objective, often termed *scientific*, criteria can *fairly* settle them *unless* there is agreement on such fairness principles that govern those involved in the division process.²⁴ Simultaneously, most chronicles of science and, in fact, of scientific integrity, demand, at a minimum, some degree of self-reflection and correlative disclosure of underlying convictions.²⁵ Because assumptions on what is perceived as fair permeate, to a greater or lesser extent, all rules on distribution, a purported scientific method of international taxation would actually do well in revealing, rather than concealing, them.

III. IT TAKES TWO TO TANGO

The fact that humans are notoriously bad at demarcating boundaries of fractions and distributing them fairly can largely be explained by reference to two elements: *unrestrained perception of value* (subjective) and the very *nature*

²¹ International tax law as a field of legal expertise largely defies traditional definitions of international/domestic and public/private law. It commonly refers to the web of double taxation agreements bilaterally signed by sovereign countries which bear direct consequences to private actors (mostly multinational enterprises). Unlike other branches of international law, it does not rely on a multilateral convention for principled guidance. Moreover, a sovereign's surrender of a portion of its power to tax is done through complex arrangements that do not fundamentally alter domestic legislation but that may significantly limit its application. See generally Klaus Vogel, *Double Tax Treaties and Their Interpretation*, 4 INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER (1986).

²² International tax scholarship has long grappled with positioning itself within the broader realm of public international law and corresponding literature. See Dirk Broekhuijsen & Irma Mosquera Valderrama, *Revisiting the Case of Customary International Tax Law*, 23 INTERNATIONAL COMMUNITY LAW REVIEW (2021); Reuven S. Avi-Yonah, *International Tax as International Law*, 57 TAX LAW REVIEW 483 (2004).

²³ This observation is particularly relevant now as present discussions on the Two Pillar Solution, especially with respect to Pillar Two, seem to be leading us astray by drawing attention to the matter of *states vs. multinational corporations* (corporate race to the bottom) as foundational. The place of multinational corporations as subjects of public international law is still sadly contentious and so, as we stand, the nation state remains, in many ways, the primordial unit of concern in matters of international affairs.

²⁴ In his enlightening review of Rawls' original position, Ronald Dworkin aptly reasoned that, although our political traditions do not require that governing principles are chosen by men in Rawls' original position in order to be acceptable, there is a presumption of fairness attached to those principles that have in fact been chosen by those whom they govern. See Ronald Dworkin, *The Original Position*, 40 THE UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO LAW REVIEW 500, 507 (1973).

²⁵ Alison Kretser, et al., *Scientific Integrity Principles and Best Practices: Recommendations from a Scientific Integrity Consortium*, 25 SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING ETHICS 327 (2019).

of the divided thing (objective). What we deem inherently valuable,²⁶ or what we think may hold value to others in a tradable way,²⁷ evidently plays a key role in any division process. Conflict seldomly arises in the partition of something that those involved find to be worthless. However, perception of value only becomes a problem if no rules on what constitutes a just division are previously agreed on.²⁸ Without consensual guidelines, the incentive to maximise one's own share of something deemed valuable will only be silenced in the face of some higher moral imperative.

The nature of things, on the other hand, imposes an actual *physical limit* to men's whims. Divisions are complicated because most, if not all, things are finite. If valuable things were inexhaustible, division would probably not be as contentious a topic as it is. But beyond that, some things are just more easily divisible than others. Take outer space, for example. Our ineptitude in slicing it up into jurisdictions²⁹ reflects, in part, the immanent difficulty of fractioning something that is, by all intents and purposes, boundless. While knowing and defining what exactly is considered *the whole* is usually the first step in any partitioning process, when things achieve a certain order of magnitude it becomes arguably more difficult to define³⁰ them. But even where largeness has been mapped out to a satisfactory degree, a precise definition of a whole may still be undesirable for practical or political reasons.³¹

The high seas, for example, are defined in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) by way of exclusion³² rather than description. The high seas are everything that is not considered to be within countries' allocated fractions of jurisdiction over the ocean space as provided for by the Convention.³³ Indefiniteness here is seemingly deployed as a means of ensuring

²⁶ Lee Anne Fennell, *Revealing Options*, 118 Harvard Law Review 1399, 1418 (2005) (highlighting the different techniques available to elicit honest evaluations of things).

²⁷ Even waste may hold value in a tradable way. See Benedetta Cotta, *What goes around, comes around? Access and allocation problems in Global North–South waste trade*, 20 INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL AGREEMENTS: POLITICS, LAW AND ECONOMICS 255 (2020).

²⁸ See Albin, *supra* note 20.

²⁹ Alexandra Harrisa & Ray Harris, *The need for air space and outer space demarcation*, 22 Space Policy 3 (2006) (analysing the different problems that relate to outer space demarcation).

³⁰ Jonathan C. McDowell, *The edge of space: Revisiting the Karman Line*, 151 ACTA ASTRONAUTICA 668 (2018).

³¹ Alex S. Li, *Ruling Outer Space: Defining the Boundary and Determining Jurisdictional Authority*, 73 Oklahoma Law Review 711 (2021) (considering the geopolitical challenges that hinder global acceptance of a demarcation line).

³² United Nations General Assembly, *Convention on the Law of the Sea*. 10 December 1982, United Nations Treaty Series, vol. 1833, no. 31363.

³³ The more recent agreement known as the High Seas Treaty follows the same methodology. The agreement's scope of application is set to 'areas beyond national jurisdiction'. See United Nations General

peaceful cohabitation on planet Earth. As long as they remain open and free³⁴ to all states, defining the high seas' *exact scope* is futile because that which is indivisible does not require meticulous boundary definitions. If, however, control over the *entire* ocean space was to be divided and shared between countries, chances are that scientifically precise definitions that rely on static snapshots of nature would not be sufficient.

IV. INTERNATIONAL TAX, YOU ARE NOT THAT SPECIAL

Resorting to social conventions or mutually agreed definitions has long been the chief way to ensure social structuring and organisation amid the process of partitioning something that is innately troublesome to define. Examples of such conventions abound: the Greenwich meridian which splits east and west in relation to an imaginary line that cuts across the United Kingdom,³⁵ the Treaty of Tordesillas which divided the entire (then-deemed) New World between Portugal and Spain,³⁶ the Berlin Conference and subsequent years during which the African continent was arbitrarily partitioned between colonising powers,³⁷ to name but a few. Inconvenience in defining something has not historically prevented powerful nations from defining the undefinable, often in disregard of others' interests, before proceeding to divide it.

Against this backdrop, the first Model Tax Conventions, the bedrock of the international tax regime, are yet another example of this long lineage of human attempts to rationalise a division process.³⁸ Taxing entitlements over cross-border wealth are a social abstraction just as much as the Gregorian calendar –

Assembly, *Agreement under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction*. New York, 19 June 2023, A/CONF.232/2023/4.

³⁴ The principle of *mare liberum*, or freedom of the high seas, was first articulated by Dutch jurist Hugo Grotius in the 17th century. See HUGO GROTIUS, *THE FREE SEA* 57 (Knud Haakonssen ed. Richard Hakluyt trans., Liberty Fund, 2004). (“(...) seeing that in the judgment of very many, both philosophers and divines, peace and justice differ rather in name than in deed and that peace is not any agreement whatsoever but a well ordered and disposed concord.”)

³⁵ CHARLES W. J. WITHERS, *ZERO DEGREES: GEOGRAPHIES OF THE PRIME MERIDIAN* 25 (Harvard University Press, 2017).

³⁶ Christopher R. Rossi, *Treaty of Tordesillas Syndrome: Sovereignty ad Absurdum and the South China Sea Arbitration*, 50 CORNELL INTERNATIONAL LAW JOURNAL 231, 268 (2017).

³⁷ Jeffrey Herbst, *The Creation and Maintenance of National Boundaries in Africa*, 43 INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION 673 (1989); Ieuan Griffiths, *The Scramble for Africa: Inherited Political Boundaries*, 152 THE GEOGRAPHICAL JOURNAL 204 (1986).

³⁸ W. H. Coates, *League of Nations Report on Double Taxation Submitted to the Financial Committee by Professors Bruins, Einaudi, Seligman, and Sir Josiah Stamp*, 87 JOURNAL OF THE ROYAL STATISTICAL SOCIETY 99 (1924) (noting the lack of economic reasoning to buttress the exemption method as the preferred mechanism to avoid double taxation).

or any other calendar, for that matter. They are not an irrefutable fact of nature such as the oceans or outer space. The entire concept of taxation is indeed a social construct.³⁹ Absolute rejection of non-double taxation as the sacrosanct rule the world must abide by was (and is) a choice made in view of the belief that stifling world trade via taxation is undesirable. Context-dependent, however, an entirely different choice⁴⁰ based on a social convention could have just as easily been made; say, the possibility of double taxation *up to an agreed point*, for example.

At their core, international taxation rules that have stubbornly persisted for over a century are about nothing other than defining a whole (generally tax jurisdiction over corporate wealth) and subsequently partitioning it (between nations). Not by chance did Klaus Vogel define rules of double taxation as *rules of limitation of law*⁴¹ rather than conflict rules. Rules of double taxation effectively demarcate individual portions of the global power to tax and distribute them among jurisdictions. Accordingly, the matter of *distribution*, and distribution alone, is the single stalk from which every other branch of discussion in international taxation should originate.

Having yielded to the fact that sharing is hard, the architects of the international tax regime have alluded to the nature of the divided thing as the prime justification for the lack of an agreeable solution to the conundrum of justly allocating taxing rights.⁴² How could we possibly define and fairly attribute portions of (taxable) corporate wealth to different countries in a global market economy? The invariable answer to this is that no single jurisdiction can exclusively lay claim⁴³ to one or more of the many concurring processes that lead to the creation of marketable things. While this argument may carry some truth,⁴⁴ it noticeably implies that we humans have not been arbitrarily defining and dividing parts of very majestic wholes, like the ocean with its

³⁹ As famously said by U.S. Justice Oliver Wendell Holmes Jr., “Taxes are what we pay for civilized society”. See *Compania General de Tabacos de Filipinas v. Collector of Internal*, 275 U.S. 87 (1927) (Holmes, J., dissenting).

⁴⁰ Ruth Mason, *The Transformation of International Tax*, 114 *American Journal of International Law* 353 (2020) (recounting the many developments that took place in the past century that led to a clear paradigm shift in what is considered acceptable in international taxation: from non-double taxation to full taxation).

⁴¹ Vogel, *INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER* (1986).

⁴² See TEO, *supra* note 7; Jogarajan, *supra* note 8; Bruins, et al., *supra* note 9.

⁴³ Michael Devereux & John Vella, *Issues of Fairness in Taxing Corporate Profit*, 2 *LSE PUBLIC POLICY REVIEW* 1 (2022).

⁴⁴ Christians, *Tax Notes International*, 4 (2018) (emphasising that, indeed, geographically fragmenting an item of income that has been produced via international trade and commerce is all but impossible).

insurmountable depth, or time with its inexorable way of moving forward, for millennia.

That the notion of formulary apportionment of corporate profit, for example, irks some⁴⁵ on principled grounds seems to ambivalently negate our very human tradition of defining the undefinable in order to divide the indivisible when push comes to shove. Contrary to that, this essay argues that the real problem with justly allocating taxing entitlements does not pertain to the actual nature of the divided thing. Rather, it relates to the first element that makes us bad at fairly demarcating and dividing fractions of a whole: unrestrained perception of value. More specifically, it relates to the absence of a (common) higher moral imperative, such as the one that underlies the need for freedom of the high seas or, at the very least, of previously agreed rules that prevent the partitioner from being the chooser.

Any efforts put into making the international tax regime more equitable should thus prioritise the formulation of overarching mechanisms that are capable of restraining nations' perception of value. Yet, somehow, we still seem to be caught up in highly convoluted conversations about the nature of the divided thing and quantitative metrics that can perfectly capture it.⁴⁶ To be sure, empirical pointers and objective criteria do have their place and relevance in most division processes, including in those seen in international taxation. But pinning the difficulty of achieving consensus to the hassle of finding the most mathematically accurate formulae misses the point entirely⁴⁷ and, worse yet, muddles the process even further.⁴⁸ To the extent that international taxation primarily concerns the aspect of distribution, it will always and necessarily be tethered to the element of perception of value. Therefore, focusing on hyper *scientific* calculations as the ideal proxy for fairness or justice seems largely inadequate because a *purely objective* conception of international taxation is simply unattainable.

⁴⁵ Zakir Akhand & Amin Mawani, *Arm's Length Principle vs. Formulary Apportionment in BEPS Action 13: Stakeholders' Perspectives*, 20 *Accounting in Europe* 225 (2023) (arguing that professional accounting firms' *explicit* lobbying against moving away from the Arm's Length Principle (ALP) towards formulary apportionment on account of complexity may conceal some *implicit* lobbying motivated by the perception that the ALP regime is more beneficial to multinational taxpayers).

⁴⁶ See OECD, *supra* note 15.

⁴⁷ Ivan Ozai, *International Equity Revisited*, 12 *Columbia Journal of Tax Law*, 83 (2020) (noting the high degree of arbitrariness that a choice of a formula for corporate profit apportionment involves).

⁴⁸ As largely evidenced by extensive commentary on how complex the new rules under the Two Pillar Solution proposed by the OECD/G20 Base Erosion Profit Shifting Project are. See Yariv Brauner, *The Return of the Phoenix? The G-7 Countries' Agreement on a 15% Minimum Tax*, 49 *INTERTAX* 750 (2021).

V. A SCIENTIFIC METHOD FOR INTERNATIONAL TAXATION?

In its usual sense,⁴⁹ the scientific method is standardly described as an iterative process wherein hypotheses are formulated, and tested, in relation to empirical observations until there is enough cohesive knowledge that allows for the development of a body of theory. Whereas deviations from this archetypal description are not infrequent and at times desirable,⁵⁰ behind every attempt at deploying the scientific method lies the unifying desire to reveal or create knowledge that is deemed *trustworthy* to a broad audience.⁵¹ In other words, the objectivity ideal of science embodies, at its heart, the pursuit of trustworthiness of knowledge claims.⁵² The pressing reality of life, however, is that hardly anything is completely objective or value-free, even science.⁵³ In addition to the circumstances that affect its production,⁵⁴ scientific knowledge notably grapples with the well-known existence of cognitive biases.

Scientists of the natural sciences, particularly the medical ones,⁵⁵ have long been conscious of the fact that biases may skew results of experiments that could otherwise be seen as empirically objective.⁵⁶ First blind and, subsequently, double-blind studies have thus become a staple in the quest to insulate the results of an experiment from researchers' and participants' proclivities.⁵⁷ Regardless of whether double-blind can be seen as a silver bullet or not,⁵⁸ it arguably

⁴⁹ While there is no single universal definition of the scientific method, the steps it involves are generally agreed upon. See BARRY GOWER, *SCIENTIFIC METHOD: AN HISTORICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL INTRODUCTION* 12-13 (Routledge, 1997).

⁵⁰ In the remit of social sciences, for example, a profusion of quantitative and qualitative tools, following deductive and inductive methods of reasoning, is widely employed in the exercise of acquiring and producing knowledge. See Betina Hollstein, *An Introduction*, in *MIXED METHODS SOCIAL NETWORKS RESEARCH: DESIGN AND APPLICATIONS (STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES)* (Silvia Domínguez & Betina Hollstein eds., 2014).

⁵¹ HEATHER E. DOUGLAS, *SCIENCE, POLICY, AND THE VALUE-FREE IDEAL* 115 (University of Pittsburgh Press, 2009).

⁵² *Id.* at, 116.

⁵³ *Id.* at, 156.

⁵⁴ Karin D. Knorr-Cetina, *Social and Scientific Method or What Do We Make of the Distinction Between the Natural and the Social Sciences?*, 11 *Philosophy of the Social Sciences* 335, 355 (1981) ("Since the choices exist throughout the process of experimentation, there is no core of the production of research which is in principle left unaffected by the circumstances of production.").

⁵⁵ Lise Lotte Gluud, *Bias in Clinical Intervention Research*, 163 *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF EPIDEMIOLOGY* 493 (2006).

⁵⁶ Torsten Wilholt, *Bias and values in scientific research*, 40 *STUDIES IN HISTORY AND PHILOSOPHY OF SCIENCE* 92 (2009).

⁵⁷ For a critical account of the development, over the centuries, of (double) blind methodology see: Ted J. Kaptchuk, *A History of Blind Assessment and Placebo Controls in Medicine*, 72 *BULLETIN OF THE HISTORY OF MEDICINE* 389 (1998).

⁵⁸ Robert Hudson, *Should We Strive to Make Science Bias-Free? A Philosophical Assessment of the Reproducibility Crisis*, 52 *JOURNAL FOR GENERAL PHILOSOPHY OF SCIENCE* 389 (2021).

provides a more reasonable alternative to obtaining expectedly objective results than that available in pre-scientific method days. What this observation relevantly shows in the context of the present discussion is that, even in sterile settings of natural experiments, biases must be mitigated and minimised before results deemed reasonably objective can be obtained.

This essay has advanced the central proposition that division processes, including those of taxing entitlements, cannot be fairly settled by reference to purely objective criteria because they necessarily involve the subjective element of perception of value. Factoring that in, a scientific method for international taxation would, accordingly, have to look for answers within domains of knowledge other than that of the natural and exact sciences. Prime candidates in offering backup hermeneutical support⁵⁹ would, surely unsurprisingly, be moral and political philosophy.⁶⁰ Rawls' hypothetical *original position*, for example, famously describes a vantage point from which individuals should decide on principles of justice.⁶¹ Notably, someone in the original position stands behind a veil of ignorance which prevents them from knowing a priori anything that may lead to an assessment of relational (dis)advantages *vis-à-vis* others.⁶² Much like double-blind methodology, the veil is then supposed to counter human nature of being driven by our own egotistical interests if left to our own devices.⁶³

In view of the degree of heterogeneity in interests⁶⁴ seen at the global level with respect to taxation, reconciling the core aspects of the scientific method with the distributional character of international taxation would admittedly require unprecedented political effort. Ideally, such reconciliation would mean

⁵⁹ Dworkin, *supra* note 24 at 505. ("It is the task of moral philosophy, according to the technique of equilibrium, to provide a structure of principles that supports these immediate convictions about which we are more or less secure, with two goals in mind. First, this structure of principles must explain the convictions by showing the underlying assumptions they reflect; second, it must provide guidance in those cases about which we have either no convictions or weak or contradictory convictions").

⁶⁰ A less conventional route would be to look for normative guidance in international human rights law, as I argue elsewhere. See Luiza Leite de Queiroz, *What normativity for international tax? Towards alignment with human rights and the Sustainable Development Goals*, in TAXATION, HUMAN RIGHTS AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENTS: GLOBAL SOUTH PERSPECTIVES (Eghosa Ekhaton, et al. eds., 2024 (forthcoming)).

⁶¹ See RAWLS, *supra* note 2.

⁶² Dworkin, *supra* note 24 at 530. ("The state of ignorance in the original position is so shaped that the antecedent interest of everyone must lie, as I said, in the same solution.").

⁶³ The age-old interdisciplinary debate on whether humans are competitive or cooperative by nature will be deliberately overlooked given the narrow scope of this essay.

⁶⁴ While biases and interests are not strictly the same, they are closely interwoven. See Don A. Moore, et al., *Conflict of interest and the intrusion of bias*, 5 JUDGMENT AND DECISION MAKING 37 (2010).

that previously agreed principles on fairness⁶⁵ would become the compass of empirical data interpretation, as well as of any assessments on data's convenience and suitability to ensure a fair division. Should that prove to be too idealistic at this time, it is interesting to think that a corrective mechanism of sorts, inspired by double-blind methodology and Rawls' original position, could perhaps bring us closer to that aspirational idea of an objective international tax regime.

One important aspect of double-blind studies is that obliviousness to the elements that may influence a participant's actions or a researcher's interpretations must already be embedded in the research design. Naturally, that is so because once important information is divulged it may be impossible to avoid bias altogether. Given that the international tax regime has been up and running for over a hundred years, one might rightfully consider whether a scientific method for international taxation could be devised this far along into the process. Cautiously, this essay argues that, if *ex ante* double-blind is no longer possible, perhaps we could consider an *ex post* alternative route that may still serve a similar purpose.

VI. BEHIND THE VEIL: DOUBLE-BLIND LEGAL AID

Stripping the idea of unrestrained perception of value down, we unsurprisingly land on the concept of power. A partitioner only gets away with being simultaneously the chooser if the neglected party does not have the capacity to protest the detrimental arrangement. Power, in this sense, may emanate from factors such as brute force, greater knowledge, previous authorisation given by a cogent source or, as is generally the case in matters of international affairs, economic preponderance and geopolitical influence. Partitioning rules of international taxation have been created by economically powerful countries and the updates we are currently witnessing in the post-Base Erosion Profit Shifting (BEPS) era are still largely driven by these countries' interests.⁶⁶

⁶⁵ Ivan Ozai: Ivan Ozai, *Origin and Differentiation in International Income Allocation*, 44 DALHOUSIE LAW JOURNAL 129 (2021); Ozai, COLUMBIA JOURNAL OF TAX LAW, (2020).

⁶⁶ As evidenced by recent analyses of the likely impacts of the Two Pillar Solution for developing countries. See Felix Reitz, *Revenue Effects of the OECD Corporate Tax Reform – An Updated Impact Assessment of Pillar Two*. St. Gallen (2023); Aitor Navarro, *The Allocation of Taxing Rights under Pillar One of the OECD Proposal*, in THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL TAX LAW (Florian Haase & Georg Kofler eds., 2023); Suranjali Tandon, *Assessing the Impact of Pillar Two on Developing Countries*, 50 INTERTAX 923 (2022); Graeme S. Cooper, *Building on the Rubble of Pillar One*, BULLETIN FOR INTERNATIONAL TAXATION 533 (2021).

If we consider that partitioning rules are legally imprinted⁶⁷ in pre-drafted versions⁶⁸ of double taxation agreements, it is reasonable to conceive that the choosing happens during bilateral negotiations of the final contours of such agreements. As a manifestation of *acta jure imperii*, negotiations are, of course, conducted by government officials on behalf of their respective countries. It could then be argued that the mere act of negotiating should suffice to ensure that the partitioner does not get to ultimately be the chooser. But, again, given the absence of constraints to countries' perception of value in international taxation, such interpretation would strike as rather reductionist.⁶⁹

It is exactly because unchecked power can influence the outcomes of a partitioning process in many sophisticated ways⁷⁰ that an exclusively objective version of international taxation can hardly exist. A less biased version, however, may perhaps be attainable. As earlier stated, a scientific method for international taxation would have to take stock of, and reconcile with, the biases that hinder international taxation's objectivity. If scientific accuracy is truly a goal moving forward, mitigating power-fuelled imbalances should be priority number one on the reforms' agenda – even if only at a procedural level at the very beginning. Ensuring that the partitioner does not get to be the chooser seems like as good a place to start as any. Fortunately, the task of imagining the outlines of a corrective double-blind-like mechanism is made much easier by the fact that important elements it should contain already exist in legal systems across the globe.

An entire branch of law – namely, modern Consumer Law –, for example, stands on the recognition that weaker parties must be protected⁷¹ in asymmetric contractual relationships. Likewise, societies based on the rule of law have long established that equality of arms⁷² in legal disputes is indeed something desirable. In fact, at its most fundamental sense, the social construct of legal

⁶⁷ Elliott Ash & Omri Marian, *The Making of International Tax Law: Empirical Evidence from Natural Language Processing* Legal Studies Research Paper Series. (demonstrating that the language of the OECD Model Tax Conventions has significantly influenced most double taxation agreements currently in force).

⁶⁸ Yariv Brauner, *Tax Treaty Negotiations: Myth and Reality*, 4 *International Tax Studies*, 13 (2021) (“It importantly revealed that only a small part of tax treaties is originally drafted during negotiations.”).

⁶⁹ *Id.* at 10. (“The survey similarly supports the doubt often cast over the myth of tax treaties as rigorous, fully-negotiated agreements among states based on an informed study of all relevant aspects and potential outcomes of the negotiations.”).

⁷⁰ Martin Hearson, *When Do Developing Countries Negotiate Away Their Corporate Tax Base?*, 30 *JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT* 233 (2018).

⁷¹ MARTIJN W. HESSELINK, *JUSTIFYING CONTRACT IN EUROPE: POLITICAL PHILOSOPHIES OF EUROPEAN CONTRACT LAW*. (Oxford University Press First Edition ed. 2021).

⁷² European Court of Human Rights, *Guide on Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights: Right to a fair trial (civil limb)* (2022).

representation symbolises the dismantling of the logic of self-defence of self-interest in the name of a minimum level of *inter partes* parity.⁷³ Most notably, many legal systems have recognised that free legal aid⁷⁴ is a pivotal driver of effective access to justice.⁷⁵ A corrective mechanism for international taxation could then be modelled after these same principles and premises.

This essay proposes an initial outline of such a mechanism centred on the concept of a transnational pool of tax experts with the sole mandate of counselling sovereigns during the pre-signature phases (including instances of renegotiation) of a double taxation agreement. The pool of experts would then act as a *transnational Advocate General's office* of sorts. First and foremost, it would have to be assembled following predetermined criteria on the level and scope of expertise needed. Ideally, it would aim to parallel in knowledge those accounting firms that currently counsel multinational enterprises on international taxation affairs. Experts would be called upon to issue documents akin to an Advocate General's opinion⁷⁶ and, at a minimum, an advisory opinion's objective should be twofold.⁷⁷

First, it should seek to flag potential risks to a country's tax base arising from different sections of a draft double taxation agreement. Secondly, it should aim at suggesting imaginable economic trade-offs in hypothetical scenarios which may be relevant for countries that, according to the assessment conducted, may be giving up too much of their taxing rights. Lesser developed countries would have priority in requesting advisory opinions from these experts. As per double-blind methodology, however, neither requesting country officials would be allowed to know who the assigned expert(s) is (are), nor would the counsellor(s) be allowed to know which country wished to receive an opinion.

⁷³ Shai Agmon, *Undercutting Justice – Why legal representation should not be allocated by the market*, 20 *POLITICS, PHILOSOPHY & ECONOMICS* 99 (2021).

⁷⁴ As famously recognised by the European Court of Human Rights in the late 1970s. See *Airey v. Ireland*, App. No. 6289/73, Eur. Ct. H.R. (Oct. 9, 1979).

⁷⁵ The Brazilian case is particularly interesting in that respect. See Rodrigo M. Nunes, *Access to Justice and the Legal Complex: Building a Public Defenders' Office in Brazil*, 12 *JOURNAL OF POLITICS IN LATIN AMERICA* 155 (2021).

⁷⁶ Namely, to opinions issued by the European Court of Justice Advocates General. On the value of their role, see Michal Bobek, *Fourth in the Court: Why Are There Advocates General in the Court of Justice*, 14 *CAMBRIDGE YEARBOOK OF EUROPEAN LEGAL STUDIES* 529 (2011-2012).

⁷⁷ The objectives here proposed are seen as a floor in light of what we know of the disparities between OECD and non-OECD countries' treaty negotiators. See Brauner, *INTERNATIONAL TAX STUDIES*, 12 (2021). ("How could negotiators maximize the economic gains from tax treaties when they are barely familiar with the economic positions of either country or the law and policies of their negotiating parties? Non-OECD negotiators essentially all claimed to negotiate treaties to promote cross-border trade and investment, for example, yet the scant economic (and scantly law) scholarship on tax treaties cast doubt on the contribution of tax treaties to cross-border investment.").

This way, advice would admittedly have to be broad but that certainly should not preclude it from being all-encompassing. Crucially, such specialised counselling would have to be provided for free or, at most, in return for a very modest fee. Financing the activities of this relevant body should not be an issue really, and funds could even come from current development aid commitments.⁷⁸ Finally, and perhaps most important of all, historical partitioners of the global power to tax would have to be fully supportive of the mechanism to ensure its feasibility and transformative potential.

VII. BONA FIDE WHERE BONA FIDE IS DUE

In anticipation of counterarguments that are sure to emphasise that relevant capacity building initiatives already exist,⁷⁹ it is important to conclude this essay by addressing two relevant points. Firstly, these initiatives and the proposal herein contained are not mutually exclusive. On the contrary, if anything, they should reinforce one another and, with some luck, be catalysts of each other's strengths. Secondly, and strictly related to the first point, not only does it take time to build capacities⁸⁰ but pursued positive outcomes are, like those of most social interventions, not immediate or instantaneous. As a narrower expression of the more holistic concept of education and training,⁸¹ capacity building generally requires long-term investment before yielding gains in the long run.⁸² While these initiatives are necessary and, for the most part, highly commendable, proper planning of a reform agenda demands consideration of different applicable timeframes.

It should be duly emphasised, in any event, that the mechanism here proposed would by no means replace the need for an earnest debate on applicable principles of fairness to the international tax regime. Simply put, it

⁷⁸ According to the latest available OECD data, in 2022 official development assistance stood at USD 204 billion, an all-time high. The increase has been partly credited to some countries' quick financial response to the refugee crisis following the war in Ukraine, which greatly illustrates the power of political will in foreign aid spending and allocation. See OECD, *Official development assistance (ODA) (2023)*, available at <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/official-development-assistance.htm>.

⁷⁹ OECD, *Building tax capacity in developing countries* (2023), available at <https://www.oecd.org/tax/tax-global/tax-capacity-building-developing-countries.htm#meetings>.

⁸⁰ Gabriele Marconi, *Education as a Long-Term Investment: The Decisive Role of Age in the Education-Growth Relationship*, 71 KYKLOS 132 (2018).

⁸¹ United Nations, *Capacity Building* (2023), available at <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>.

⁸² Jong-Wha Lee & Hanol Lee, *Human capital in the long run*, 122 JOURNAL OF DEVELOPMENT ECONOMICS 147 (2016); ROBERT J. BARRO & JONG-WHA LEE, *EDUCATION MATTERS: GLOBAL SCHOOLING GAINS FROM THE 19TH TO THE 21ST CENTURY* (Oxford University Press. 2015).

would only represent a step in the right direction of remedying biases in the meantime. Time and, in fact, timing are of essence when it comes to the distribution of the spoils of globalisation-spurred economic growth. More than the so-called hard sciences' approach, this essay would suggest that what we truly need in international taxation are bona fide interactions. Sharing is tricky but it can also be caring. In a middle-class family reality, a larger portion of scrambled eggs or birthday cake for one well-fed child merely means a smaller portion for another equally well-fed child. A larger share of taxing entitlements for a certain group of countries over a significant period of time, however, means less taxing rights, and connected tax revenues, for another group of countries.

A century ago, the baseline assumption for wanting to avoid double taxation at all costs was that increased transnational corporate activity would be worthwhile for everyone everywhere. If that assumption is in any way to still be confirmed, caring about sharing is more necessary now, amid reforms' efforts, than ever. Biases embedded into the fabric of international taxation largely contribute to higher levels of socioeconomic distress in already impecunious places. And, paraphrasing Brazilian sociologist Herbert de Souza, those who are hungry are in a hurry and cannot wait for structural solutions forever.⁸³

⁸³ World History Archives, *Speech delivered by Herbert de Souza (Betinho) at the Plenary of the United Nations during the Second Session of the Preparatory Committee for the Social Summit, New York, August 23, 1994* (2023), available at <http://www.hartford-hwp.com/archives/42/089.html>.